

THE ROLE OF ANWAR PASHA IN THE HISTORY OF TURKESTAN

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Abstract. This article talks about Anwar Pasha, who came to Turkestan and fought to free it from the Red Army. In addition, his life path, bravery, assessments given by domestic and foreign historians are critically described. Through this article, you can get more detailed information about the personality of Anwar Pasha.

Key words: Ottoman Empire, Young Turks, Union and Development, Comintern, USSR, Council of People's Supervisors, Central Executive Committee.

РОЛЬ АНВАР-ПАШИ В ИСТОРИИ ТУРКЕСТАНА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассказывается об Анвар-паше, который пришел в Туркестан и боролся за его освобождение от Красной Армии. Кроме того, критически освещены его жизненный путь, отвага, оценки, данные отечественными и зарубежными историками. Благодаря этой статье вы можете получить подробную информацию о личности Анвара-паши.

Ключевые слова: Османская империя, младотурки, Союз и развитие, Коминтерн, СССР, Совет народного контроля, ЦИК.

INTRODUCTION

For more than 130 years, our country lived under the tyranny of Tsarist Russia, and then the former Soviets. Our forefathers who fought for the liberation of the Motherland such as Polatkhan, Dukchi Eshon, Baba Goklan, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, Abdulla Avloni, Munavvarqori and Cholpon, who called our people to enlightenment, were persecuted by the authoritarian regime. physically destroyed. All the works written by them were burned, everything they did was condemned. The Jadidic movement was also completely destroyed. In 1918-1935, the national-liberation movement against the Soviet regime was called "printing" by the Bolsheviks. However, one thing should not be forgotten that our people won their freedom despite famine, repressions and wars, just like the sun shines after darkness. On August 31, 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan was established as an independent state. Our country was recognized by the world community one after another. The Republic of Turkey is the first country to recognize Uzbekistan in the world. Our relations with the fraternal Turkish people, whose language and religion are common, go back several centuries. Our ancestors traded, and diplomatic relations between our countries have not stopped. During the struggle against the Bolsheviks in Turkestan in 1918-1935, many Turkish military officers came to our country and prepared our young men for military exercises and battles. One such person, military commander Anwar Pasha [22.11.1881, Istanbul - 4.08.1922, Eastern Bukhara, Baljuvan.] is one of the selfless people who are visible not only in Turkey or Turkestan, but in the whole Muslim world. At the beginning of the 20th century, no one's fame in the Muslim world was as widespread as his. Anwar Pasha took part in political processes in Turkey, Macedonia, Caucasus, Germany, Russia, Turkestan and Bukhara. Anwar Pasha was born in Istanbul in 1881 as the first child in the family of a small servant Ahmadbey. Anwar Pasha graduated from the military academy in Istanbul in 1903. The

Academy sent him to serve in the 3rd Army stationed in Macedonia under the Ottoman Empire.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Anvar Pasha's origin is Macedonian, and his childhood was spent here. Anvar Pasha Ottoman Sultan Abdulhamid II [1842-1918; was one of the leaders of the Young Turks movement that fought against the sultan and the caliphate: 1876-1909]. After the "Ittihad and Progress" party seized power in the Macedonian sultanate on July 23, 1908, Anwar, who was at the center of these events, became a national hero. In that year, Anwar, who was not yet 27 years old, was given the general military title - Pasha. Anwar Pasha's prestige and influence, his influence, grew rapidly. Anwar Pasha was appointed Turkish military attache in Berlin. He studied the German language and military art. During the Italo-Turkish War [September 1911 - October 1912] and the Balkan Wars [October 1912 - August 1913], Anwar Pasha showed bravery in the battles of the Ottoman Turkish Empire against Italy, Bulgaria, and Serbia. As a result of the military coup in January 1913, the country was completely handed over to the Young Turks. Tal'at Pasha, Anwar Pasha and Jamal Pasha began to rule the country. Tal'at Pasha was the Prime Minister of the Ottoman Empire, Anwar Pasha was the country's Commander-in-Chief and Minister of War, and Jamal Pasha [1872-1922] was the Minister of the Navy. They worked in these positions until the end of 1918. Anwar Pasha was the chief of staff of the military corps during the Balkan wars. Major Mustafa Kemal Atatürk[1881-1938; presidential period: 1923-1938] also served. During the Second Balkan War [June-August 1913], Anwar Pasha's troops hit the Bulgarians hard. The city of Edirne, which was taken from Turkey in the first war, was liberated from the Bulgarians. Mahmudhoja Behbudi [1875-1919], who went to Edirne in 1914, sincerely describes the military exploits of Anvar Pasha in his "Travel Memories" published in "Oyna" magazine at that time as follows:...Anvarbek walked a four-day journey in one day, conquered Edirne and took it back from the Bulgarians. When the Bulgarians found out about this, they set fire to the well-to-do areas, rooms, and warehouses of Edirne. they took many cannons as loot... In conclusion, the honor of Edirne's recapture went to the Young Turks and Anvar Pasha." On his part, Anvar Pasha looked favorably on the students who came from Turkestan to study in Turkey. Anvar Pasha received Osman Khoja, who came to this country from Bukhara, as a family. Anwar Pasha was appointed the Minister of War of Turkey in 1913, and the Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the entire Ottoman Turkish Army after the outbreak of the First World War. On March 5, 1914, an unforgettable event happened in Anwar's life. He married Najiba Begum, the daughter of the Ottoman sultan. Turkey's rapprochement with Germany ultimately ended with both sides concluding an accord against the Entente on August 2, 1914. Turkey entered World War 1 on the side of Germany. It should be mentioned that Anwar Pasha had a certain contribution in this rapprochement. Anwar Pasha's army went to war on two fronts: against Russia in the Caucasus and against England in Iraq, Hijaz, Egypt and Syria. Anvar Pasha personally commanded the battles on the Caucasian front. In December 1914, there were fierce battles between Turks and Russians around Sarikamish. At the same time, the two countries moved their operations to the territory of Iran, and the Turkish army defeated the Russians in Iran-Azerbaijan. V. A. Gordlevsky, a Russian scientist who was in Turkey at that time and understood the situation in the country well [later he became an academician], in his work "Silhouettes of Turkey" [1914] described Anwar Pashoni as a "hero", "of the Young Turks" party. the most famous person", he did not say for nothing. However, after

the defeat of Turkey and its allies in the First World War, Anwar Pasha and his loyal comrades Tal'at Pasha [1874-1921; He was killed by an unknown Armenian terrorist in Berlin on March 16, 1921.] and Jamal Pasha [1872-1922; On July 21, 1922, Karapet was killed by Armenian terrorists in Tiflis.] left the Turkish territory on the night of November 3, 1918. Anwar Pasha arrived in Berlin at the beginning of 1919. In July, the Istanbul military court sentenced the three pashas and their friends Nozimbek to death in absentia. Soon after that, this sentence was found to be groundless. Germany also cannot create conditions for Anwar Pasha. After that, Anwar Pasha left for Moscow. He entered Moscow by car and was immediately taken by Zinoviev to participate in the Congress of the Eastern Peoples to be held in Baku on September 1-7, 1920. G. Y. Zinoviev [1883-1936] was the chairman of the Executive Committee of the Comintern [Communist International], and on the instructions of Lenin, he led the activities of the congress in Baku. Although Anwar Pasha will participate in the congress, Zinoviev will not give him a chance to speak even after two days of arguments. Only the text of the speech prepared by Anwar Pasha will be read by Efandizoda. Munavvargari later wrote in his memoirs that he met Anwar Pasha twice during the congress. The participants of the congress will welcome Anwar Pasha with great respect, in particular, there will be sincere dialogues between him and Muslim delegates from Turkestan. Chairman of the Comintern G. Y. Zinoviev does not allow the former chairman of the national government of Bashkortostan, Validi, to participate in the work of this conference. The period of Anwar Pasha's cooperation with Soviet Russia [summer 1920 - September 1921] constitutes the darkest and most confusing pages of his biography. To be fair, there are conflicting opinions, conflicting assessments and interpretations about Anwar Pasha in books written abroad and in our country. In these works, truth and fiction are so mixed that separating them from each other requires a difficult task and hard work from the historian. Anwar Pasha and his two comrades, who were on their way to Eastern Bukhara, were received by the commander of the independence movement, Mulla Nafis, near Qilikol near Karshi. On November 9, 1921, Anwar Pasha made a statement for the first time on the land of Bukhara, joining the ranks of the national independence movement in Turkestan. The text of this statement is quoted by our compatriot Abdulla Rajab: "Comrades! I have come to join the struggle for the sacred claim of Turkestan. If there are those among you who want to serve with us, I invite them to take an oath! But if there are those among you who think that their children are under the hands of the Russians and show hesitation, let them say it openly." started in the center. Through the regions of Karshi and Sherabad, Anwar Pasha moved towards Eastern Bukhara. When Anwar Pasha reached Qabadiyan, his friend Hasan Efandi, the military inspector of Sherabad region, former colonel of the Turkish army, and Osman Efandi, the head of the Termiz militia, joined him with their squads. Anwar Pasha united with the Togay Sari group, which was primarily located in Jillikol in Eastern Bukhara. At that time, Anwar Pasha had 160 horsemen at his disposal. At first, Pasha was well received by the pro-independence people and supporters of Said Olim Khan. But after the party, the relationship changes. Anwar Pasha and his horsemen were disarmed by the order of Ibrahimbek [one of the major commanders in Bukhara]. As for Pasha himself, he is kept in captivity in the residence in Koktash. After the strong demands of the emir of Bukhara Said Olimkhan and the emir of Afghanistan Amonullah Khan and the military units of the Republic of Bukhara, Ibrahimbek released Anwar Pasha after a month of captivity. From the end of December 1921, Anwar Pasha took over the leadership of the guard

squads in Eastern Bukhara. He called a congress of all fighters from East Bukhara, as well as from Bukhara, Fergana and Matcho, who are active in Gharm region, in Koktash. At this congress, Anwar Pasha announced that his main goal was to fight against the Soviet regime, and that the national independence movement had begun to rid the land of Turkestan of the invading Red Army. Anwar Pasha established contact with the commanders in the entire territory of Turkestan. At the end of 1921, there were 20,000 people under Anwar Pasha. In the second half of 1921, Pasha gathered an army of 10,000 people around the city of Dushanbe. The siege of Dushanbe began. Anwar Pasha and Ibrahimbek were now leading the fighting. After Anwar Pasha gathered all the independence forces in Eastern Bukhara under his hand, he launched a last decisive attack to liberate Dushanbe. His first great victory was his march on Dushanbe with 1500 soldiers against 7-8 thousand people. As a result of fierce battles, on the night of February 16, 1922, the red soldiers left Dushanbe and settled in Boysun on February 22. The city passed into the hands of the pro-independence forces. The entire territory of Tajikistan in eastern Bukhara and cities and villages of Surkhandarya oasis such as Yurchi, Denov, Mirshodi, Kakaydi, Zharkurgan, Kumkurgan, Khotinrabet, Pattakesar, Sherabad passed into the hands of Anwar Pasha's soldiers. Due to the radical change in the situation in Eastern Bukhara in favor of the independentists, at the joint meeting of the All Bukhara Central Executive Committee, the Council of People's Supervisors and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Ukraine on January 2, 1922, the Emergency Dictatorship of the Central Committee of the USSR MIK over Eastern Bukhara decided to create a commission. The main goal of this commission was to destroy the pro-independence forces and restore Soviet power in the reoccupied territories. Anwar Pasha, in turn, in February 1922, to Shermuhammadbek, the commander-in-chief of the independentists in the Ferghana Valley, Daniyolbek, Jabborbek, Khaliqbek, the chiefs of the independentists around Shahrisabz, as well as to Bahrombek, Ochilbek, and Osmanbek in the Samarkand region, as well as to Khorezm. Addressing Junaid Khan with special letters, he offered to unite the army of independentists in the entire Turkestan region into a single command. At the beginning of March, a group of 100 people led by Mahmoud Rozi arrived at Anwar Pasha's disposal by Shermuhammadbek. At this time, the command of the Red Army gathered an army of 40-50 thousand people in the direction of Kogon. Anwar Pasha prepared for defensive battles. By March 1922, a common front of pro-independence forces was formed under the leadership of Anwar Pasha in a vast area from Ferghana and Samarkand regions to Eastern Bukhara and Khorezm. In the autumn of 1921, the independence activists in Bukhara and Karmana regions intensified their activities. An army of 2,000 men led by Mulla Abdul Qahhar and Jabbar Qorboshi first attacked the city of Karmana. After capturing the city, the pro-independence forces marched to Gijduvan and captured it as well. At the end of 1921, almost all of Western Bukhara was transferred to Mulla Abdul Qahhar. He maintains constant contact with Anwar Pasha and Ibrahimbek guards. In a short time, thousands of young men from Bukhara will join the army of Mulla Abdul Qahhar: 6,000 people from the vicinity of Bukhara, 2,000 people from Vobkent district, 2,000 people from Qiziltepa district, 2,000 people from Shofrikom district, 2,000 people from Pirmast district, 2,500 people from Romitan and Peshko districts, Kogon 2,000 people from the district, it reached 25,000 people with the army of Mulla Abdul Qahhar. His main goal was to capture the city of Bukhara and unite with Anwar Pasha's troops. As a result of fierce battles around the district of Gijduvan, Mullah Abdulkahar's army dealt a

heavy blow to the Red soldiers: within a month, 2,000 automatic rifles, 100,000 rounds of ammunition, 10 machine guns and 3 iron-clad armored vehicles were captured from the Bolsheviks. The territory of Nurota also passed into the hands of the pro-independence forces. At the beginning of March 1922, the independence fighters attacked the city of Bukhara. At the same time, Abdulhamid Oripov, the military inspector of the Republic of Bukhara, joined the ranks of the independents with 60 Bukhara, Turkish, Indian people and a lot of weapons. The soldiers of the Bukhara government were defeated in a one-day battle near the Zarafshan bridge. After the defeat, the Red soldiers retreated to the capital. Encouraged by the victory, the army of the leader of Mullah Abdul Qahhar attacked the capital of the Republic, Bukhara. As a result, the city of Bukhara was captured. In order to consolidate his victory, Mulla Abdul Qahhar divided his army into two parts and sent the first group of them to the city of Kogon.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Located at a railway junction and 12 miles from Old Bukhara, this city had an important strategic position. Tarjimon If the city of Kogon was captured by the independents, the aid coming to the red soldiers would be cut off. After a battle lasting more than ten hours, the city of Kogon and the settlement of Bahauddin Naqshband were liberated. However, the red soldiers gathered a sufficient number of troops and at first crushed the forces of the rebels around Kogon. Unfortunately, the troops sent by Anwar Pasha could not reach Bukhara through Shahrisabz and Karshi. Cavalrymen of General Budyani, who arrived in Bukhara from Transcaspia, entered into battle with the pro-independence forces on March 8. Additional support forces arrived from Samarkand and Tashkent and joined the red soldiers. On March 9, the Turkestan Front sent another 12,000 soldiers and several armored trains to Bukhara. In the decisive battle in Bukhara city on March 11, the pro-independence forces were defeated. In the spring of 1922, Anwar Pasha stepped up military operations and besieged the city of Boysun. Encouraged by Anwar Pasha's victories in Eastern Bukhara, Said Olim Khan appointed him as the "Supreme Commander of all troops in Bukhara" in a letter written on March 22, 1922. On March 28, Anwar Pasha himself received this letter from the representatives of Said Olim Khan. Anwar Pasha, while leading the struggle of the independents in Bukhara, did not limit himself to fighting. His letter addressed to the representative of the Bolsheviks, O. Akchurin, contains the following lines: "We, the representatives of the people of the truly independent land of Bukhara, inform you that we will continue the fight until you leave our country. For the time being, in order not to shed blood in vain, we invite you to leave our country." In the middle of April, a delegation of 10 people from the People's Commissariat of Foreign Affairs of Soviet Russia came to make peace with Anwar Pasha. At Pasha's residence, their son Usman Aka from Boysun brought their proposal. According to this truce, it was recognized that Anwar Pasha could build an independent state based on his dream in cities and regions such as Darvaz, Karategin, Kolob, Dushanbe, Hisar. In return, they demanded that he no longer interfere in the Turkestan issue. Anwar Pasha answered the Soviet ambassador on April 19 as follows: the peace agreement can be spoken only after the Russian soldiers leave the territory of Turkestan. Anwar Pasha started active military operations on May 13. The parts of the Red Army stationed in Bukhara were united, and additional soldiers were brought to help them. Bloody battles began between the two. On June 9, 1922, troops of the Bukhara group under the command of Kakurin attacked Anwar Pasha's army, which had been besieging Boysun for 4 months. As a result of these battles, the

independence fighters lost 217 people. The counterattack on June 12 was stopped by the red soldiers. The Soviet government managed to create discord between the leaders. Ibrahimbek took his army of 7,000 men on the eve of the attack of the Red Soldiers in Boysun. As a result, the main forces of the Red Akars went to a decisive battle on June 15. 200 pro-independence people were killed in the battle, 20 people were captured. Nevertheless, on the night of June 24, Anwar Pasha attacked the 8,000-strong Soviet division of General Kakurin with his 3,000-strong army around Darband, and it was crushed. Anwar Pasha united all his forces and attacked the red soldiers on June 29, but this attack was also repulsed. Fierce fighting continued in July. On July 14, 1,500 pro-independence forces attacked to liberate Sangtoda. Red soldiers repulsed this attack, 50 of the rebels were killed. On July 14, the city of Dushanbe was occupied by red soldiers. By the end of July, the independence fighters suffered huge losses, some of them came and settled in Baljuvan under the leadership of Anvar Pasha. The emir of Afghanistan Amonullah Khan sent 300 people to Anwar Pasha and invited him to his country, but Pasha gave the following answer: "I will definitely stay here." If I die, earth will be found in the land of my friends. Leaving here would be a big mistake. I gave permission for your soldiers to return." Only the brave Davlatmandbek and his men remained at Anwar Pasha's disposal. Friday, August 4, 1922 coincided with Eid al-Adha. This date was the tenth day of Zul Hijjah, 1345 Hijri. Anwar Pasha with a small detachment was in the village of Obi Dara, located 12 miles northeast of Baljuvan. After the Kurban Hayit prayer, Anvar Pasha said the following words to his comrades: "I cannot distribute Eid to you now. If a few words were written about our brotherhood, I would willingly put my stamp on it and sign it. I think that these words would be a wonderful memory of the military brotherhood in our national struggle for freedom." they said. Anwar Pasha took his 100 warriors and destroyed the 1st squadron of the 18th Cavalry Regiment. However, in the battle with the fighters of the 3rd squadron, Anwar Pasha was wounded in five places and died. Pasha killed 11 Russian soldiers with his sword in the last battle of that day. More than 25,000 people gathered at Anwar Pasha's funeral in Baljuvan. Anwar Pasha died for the independence of Turkestan.

CONCLUSION

Cholpon writes the "Baljuvan" march dedicated to the death of Anvar Pasha:

It was Baljuvan who blackened and filled it.

He painted the last hope with blood.

Oh, what bad times have come!

This rallying cry was published in full in the press of Uzbekistan on June 10, 1995 in the first issue of the newspaper <<National revival.>>. Anwar Pasha writes his last letter to his wife, Najiba Beg, in Baljuvan: "You know that, as the wretched people who spread slander about me claimed, I came to these distant lands to seek wealth, to become rich, or to establish my own power." no. It is a sacred task that the Holy One, who took me away from you and brought me to these places, entrusted to me." Many of our ancestors sacrificed their lives for the freedom of the country. In 1918-1935, Turkestans who died and were wounded made up 1,200,000 people. Russia in the guise of the USSR lost more time to re-conquer Turkestan compared to the first, and made a lot of material and moral sacrifices. The Red Army lost approximately 400,000 soldiers and officers in these battles. 1.5 million from Turkestan. a person went abroad as an emigrant. In conclusion, it should be said that every historian, when he tackles a topic, should

cover it objectively, from all sides, in his work all aspects: whether negative, should not be overlooked, be it positive. Only if this is done, we will be able to fully reveal our history to the growing generation. Only a mentally and physically mature generation that has a deep understanding of its history, lives with confidence in the future, can develop the country.

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